

Women in Digital Entrepreneurship: Bibliometric Study.

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Abstract

The rapid development of digital technologies has impacted the entrepreneurship world, this evolution offers more opportunities to women to engage in business. Advancements in technology have enabled women entrepreneurs to transcend barriers to market access and resource acquisition, thereby fostering the development of women-led enterprises across multiple sectors. As a consequence, Women entrepreneurs are widely recognized as important contributors to economic development, innovation, and social empowerment. The present study aims to investigate the research on women and digital entrepreneurship through a bibliometric approach. A total of 216 documents were extracted from the Scopus database, analyzed through VOS viewer software and MS Excel covering the period from 2017 to 2025. The study examines the most prolific authors, top-cited journals, the most contributing countries, and the research trend. Furthermore, co-authorship and co-occurrence were conducted to map the intellectual structure of knowledge in women and digital entrepreneurship. The results indicate the growing scholarly interest in women and digital entrepreneurship with significant contributions from both developed and developing countries researchers. The analysis demonstrates that the presence of interdisciplinary research, linking entrepreneurship with fields such as technology, innovation, and gender studies. This paper provides valuable bibliometric insights to the existing literature and offers directions for future studies, particularly in underexplored areas.

Keywords

women entrepreneurship, bibliometric analysis, women, digital entrepreneurship, VOS viewer

Introduction

Female entrepreneurship is considered a strategic priority and an essential driver for the empowerment of women in business, as well as for promoting the economic development of countries and sustainable development (Minniti & Nardone, 2007; Naguib, 2022; Ogundana et al., 2021). Women entrepreneurs represented nearly 40% of entrepreneurs worldwide and their businesses generated an estimated annual revenue of 25,000 billion dollars (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor 2022). Several studies have shown that women owners contribute to advancing innovation and boosting business survival prospects (Cunningham et al., 2017; Weber & Zulehner, 2010). The rapid evolution of digital landscape offers distinctive prospects for entrepreneurs to initiate and expand their ventures. Notably, women are occupying a central role, disrupting conventional gender norms and contributing to the enhancement of heterogeneity and development. Traditionally, women have encountered systemic barriers to entrepreneurial participation, including restricted availability of financial capital, unequal opportunities in access to learning, professional development, and prevailing socio-cultural norms that reinforce gender disparities (Raghuvanshi et al., 2017; THE World BANK 2020). Technological advancements have reduced the traditional obstacles that limit the participation of women in business creation. They facilitate women's access to critical information, engagement with markets, and the expansion of their professional networks. This promotes equity for women. The engagement of women in digital entrepreneurial activities represents a dynamic and evolving field of academic research. This area includes various dimensions such as access to finance, networking opportunities, skill development, access to technology, and the impact on socio-economic outcomes (Hatak et al., 2015; Raghuvanshi et al., 2017). Examining the complexities of women's engagement in digital entrepreneurship is essential for formulating effective policies and targeted interventions to support their success. Bibliometric analysis is a widely utilized and rigorous approach to investigate and examine extensive quantities of scientific information (Donthu et al., 2021; Ellegaard & Wallin, 2015; Khan & Muktar, 2020; Merigó et al., 2015). This methodology facilitates the identification of novel trends and patterns of collaboration, pertinent documents, and information sources related to a certain study topic. By employing maps, charts, and tables, bibliometric analysis effectively scans, extracts, and presents information in a comprehensible manner (Donthu et al., 2021; Khan & Muktar, 2020). There were many bibliometric studies conducted on digital entrepreneurship. For example: "Digital entrepreneurship: global maps and trends of research" (Zhai et al., 2023), "A study of digital entrepreneurship through bibliometric visualizing from 1993 to 2019" (Purnomo et al., 2020), "Clarifying the Field of Digital Entrepreneurship: Systematic Literature Review with Bibliometric Methods" ("Clarifying the

Field of Digital Entrepreneurship,” 2023). These previous bibliometric studies have helped us understand research trends and key topics related to digital entrepreneurship. In addition, a systematic literature review has shown that studies in female digital entrepreneurship are divergent and fragmented, with scarce research on cross-country comparisons and the impact of gender (Alhajri & Aloud, 2023).

The objective of this study is to conduct a bibliometric analysis of the literature from 2017 to 2025 in the field of women’s digital entrepreneurship. First, it traces the evolution of research in this field. Second, it identifies the most influential journals, publications, and authors based on citation impact criteria. Third, it provides an analysis of co-citations and author co-occurrence to map out the intellectual and conceptual landscape of the field. Finally, this research highlights emerging themes and existing gaps to suggest avenues for future research.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. The first section outlines the research methodology. The second section presents the results generated using VOSviewer software. The final section discusses the findings, outlines the study’s limitations, and suggests directions for future research.

1. Materials and Methods

1.1 Database and study scope :

The Scopus database was selected for this investigation because to its extensive publication coverage and thorough ongoing evaluation system for scientific journals, both of which support the upkeep of research standards (Schotten et al., 2017). The current investigation considers only studies relevant to female entrepreneurship. This research primarily addresses women and digital entrepreneurship only. All digital entrepreneurship related to men was excluded.

1.2 Article research criteria

Various search terms were employed to locate pertinent articles within the Scopus database. The search was conducted using the following keywords to limit the results to just articles and reviews. Our initial collection of documents in Scopus was produced using the subsequent keyword string:

TITLE-ABS-KEY (((women OR female) AND (digital OR "e-entrepreneurship") AND entrepreneur*)) AND PUBYEAR > 2016 AND PUBYEAR < 2026 AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBSTAGE , "final")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "BUSI")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English"))).

1.3 Results generation

Following data extraction from the Scopus database, an excel file containing the data was saved. The information includes the abstract keywords, citation details, author name and affiliation, and document title. Subsequently, the authors conducted their own analysis using this Excel file. One of the commonly used tools for bibliometric mapping created by (Glänzel, Van Eck & Waltman, 2017) is VOSviewer, a software for bibliometric mapping that was utilized for bibliometric analysis. This program was utilized by the majority of researchers (Ellegaard & Wallin, 2015; Fachada et al., 2022; Khan & Muktar, 2020), to create bibliometric networks for their investigations. Figure 1 illustrates the present research's sequential steps.

Figure 1: Process of conducting the Bibliometric Analysis

Source: Authors

2. Results

The following section provides an overview of the findings obtained from the conducted analyses, as previously mentioned. The outcomes are presented in a systematic manner, aligning with the research questions. The presentation of the analyses encompasses the utilization of graphs, tables, and the visualization of bibliometric networks. Additionally, a comprehensive discussion is provided for each analysis, accompanied by the corresponding results.

2.1. Annual Distribution of Scholarly Publications on Women's Digital Entrepreneurship (2017–2025)

This section presents the research findings and addresses the questions articulated in the introduction. This graph shows the distribution of publications within the domain of women and digital entrepreneurship. We show that we have an exponential growth of the publication from 3 documents in 2017 to 60 documents in 2025. which demonstrates an increasing interest in this topic in the last 3 years. This can be explained by several factors, mainly technological development, the digitalization of the economy and the emergence of new business models, as well as growing interest in gender issues and inclusion in the digital world.

Figure 2: Distribution by year

Source: Authors

2.2 The Most Influential Journals and Scholars in Women and Digital Entrepreneurship Research

The Scopus database was searched to find the ten journals in this area that were cited the most specific information about journals including Total Publication, Total Publication in the field of women and digital entrepreneurship, Table 1 shows the number of citations, the score for each citation, the SCImago journal rank, the source-normalized impact per paper, and the name of the publisher. The “*Emerald Emerging Markets Case Studies*”, published by Emerald Publishing, has the greatest volume of publications in the field of women in digital entrepreneurship, with 11 publications, 580 total publications overall, and 211 citations. This is followed by “*International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*”, published by Emerald Publishing, with 9 publications in the field, 82 total publications, and 691 citations. In addition, the “*Small Business Economics*” has 8 publications related to women and digital entrepreneurship, 646 total publications, and 10654 citations. Moreover, the distribution of the most productive journals related to women and digital entrepreneurship is shown in Table 1. Question two of the research also found the most prolific authors in women and digital entrepreneurship. The top ten authors were found using the Scopus database. A list showing the most active authors in this field is given. A list of the authors, including Author Name, Total Publications, h-Index, Total Citations, Current Affiliation, Most Cited Article, and Country, is illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2 shows a list of the most active authors in women and digital entrepreneurship. The Scopus database indicates that the most prolific author was McAdam, Maura from Ireland, who had, during the investigative phase, a total of 82 publications, 4390 citations, and an h-index of 34. The second most productive author was Orser, Barbara Jayne from Canada, who published 49 papers, received 2181 citations, and has an h-index of 24. She was followed by Peter, Serin who published 4 papers, received 26 citations, and has an h-index of 2. Furthermore, A ranking of the most prolific authors in women and digital entrepreneurship is provided in Table 2.

Table 1: Top ten productive journals

Journal name	TP	TC	TP in the field	CiteScore	Publisher	SJR	SNIP
Emerald Emerging Markets Case Studies	580	211	11	0.4	Emerald Publishing	0.160	0.089
International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship	82	691	9	8.4	Emerald Publishing	1.009	1.628
Small Business Economics	646	10654	8	16.5	Springer Nature	3.025	2.942
Journal of Women's Entrepreneurship and Education	97	317	7	3.3	Institute of Economic Sciences	0.259	0.571
Administrative Sciences	937	5239	6	5.6	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)	0.706	1.261
Cogent Business and Management	2075	10257	6	4.9	Cogent OA	0.596	1.162
Journal of Women's Entrepreneurship and Education	97	317	6	3.3	Institute of Economic Sciences	0.259	0.571
Problems and Perspectives in Management	805	2635	5	3.3	LLC CPC Business Perspectives	0.291	0.645
Humanities and Social Sciences Communications	3327	14131	5	4.2	Springer Nature	0.810	1.443

SJR: SCImago Journal Rank **SNIP:** Source Normalized Impact per Paper and Publisher

Source: Authors

Table 2: Top relevant authors in women and digital entrepreneurship

	Author	Total publication	Total citation	h-Index	Most cited article	Time cited	Country
1	McAdam, Maura	82	4390	34	Digital girl: cyberfeminism and the emancipatory potential of digital entrepreneurship in emerging economies	141	Ireland
2	Orser, Barbara Jayne	49	2181	24	Technology adoption and gender-inclusive entrepreneurship education and training	87	Canada
3	Peter, Serin	4	26	2	Unveiling the nexus: Financial inclusion, financial literacy, and financial performance as catalyst for women-owned enterprises in India	12	India
4	Ratten, Vanessa	520	11445	60	Internationalization Through Digital Empowerment for Women Filigree Jewelry Artisan Entrepreneurs in Portugal	10	Australia
5	Al-Ayed, Sura I.	35	268	10	Effect of digital opportunity recognition on students' digital entrepreneurial intentions and behavior	4	Saudi Arabia
6	Alakaleek, Wejdan	13	173	6	Navigating gender and culture in constructing network ties: perceptions and behaviors of women founders in Jordanian digital businesses	3	Jordan
7	Antoni, Darius	30	228	8	Women entrepreneurship in the developing country: The effects of financial and digital literacy on SMEs' growth	45	Indonesia
8	Antonijević, Marija	5	59	3	Average Matching Levels for Two DigComp Competence Areas of the Female Entrepreneurs in Serbia	12	Serbia
9	Asmuni,	2	11	1	Determinants of Digital Technology Adoption Among Women Entrepreneurs	10	Indonesia

10	Bernhard, Iréne	38	335	9	Keeping up the pace of digitalization in small businesses–Women entrepreneurs' knowledge and use of social media	105	Sweden
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Source: Authors

2.3 Geographical Distribution of Research on Women’s Digital Entrepreneurship

The principal aim of the third research question was to ascertain the nations that have made the most contributions to the field of research on women and digital entrepreneurship. Figure 3 shows a map that highlights the top countries in terms of TP, using information from the Scopus database. Figure 4 provides a summary overview of the most significant countries for women engaged in digital entrepreneurial activities. Furthermore, This research investigated the network of co-authorship between countries in the field of digital entrepreneurship as it relates to women. The United Kingdom demonstrated the most extensive collaborative linkages in terms of co-authorship among countries. There were 24 connections involving 26 papers and 1089 total citations. As shown in Figure 5, United States had the second highest level of connections, with 13 links to other countries, involving 25 papers and 472 total citations. International co-authorship patterns for additional countries are also visualized within the map.

Figure 3: Map of significant countries in women and digital entrepreneurship

Source: Authors

Figure 4: Distribution of the countries by documents

Source: Authors

Figure 5: Co-authorship with countries

Source: Authors

According to the figures 3 and 4 the three most significant nations are India, United Kingdom, United States. India has the highest number of documents 27, United Kingdom is second with 26 documents, and United States is third with 25 documents. The geographic distribution shows that

research on women and digital entrepreneurship is currently concentrated in developed countries, with growing participation from emerging economies. This suggests a need for more inclusive global research efforts, especially in underrepresented regions, to ensure diverse perspectives and equitable development in women and digital entrepreneurship.

2.4 Analysis of Author Keywords in Research on Women and Digital Entrepreneurship

This particular network (figure 6) shows relationships between terms used in scholarly articles about digital entrepreneurship and women. The circles represent the terms, and the size of the circle corresponds to how often the term appears in the articles. Lines connecting the circles indicate that the terms appear together frequently. It is worth exploring what lies behind the term digital entrepreneurship, as it is intertwined with a lot of other concepts. The network visualization is divided into four number of distinct thematic concentrations within the field, which also reflect the interrelated clusters.

Red Cluster: Digital Ecosystems: This cluster focuses on the modern tools used by women in business, like Digital marketing, e-commerce, social media, digital entrepreneurship, and digital skills. There is a strong connection between "covid-19" and these digital terms, suggesting that much of this research explores how the pandemic forced women entrepreneurs to shift to online platforms.

Green/Yellow cluster: Development & Literacy: Dominated by the central node of "entrepreneurship," this cluster underscores the structural and economic prerequisites for business success. It links innovation and technology to the critical pillars of financial literacy and financial inclusion. which are fundamental factors for entrepreneurial success, and with the introduction of technology and the development of digital platforms, this has helped women entrepreneurs to innovate.

Blue cluster: Sociological Perspectives: This group focuses on aspects related to sociology and ideology, and more specifically on the evolution of women's status and empowerment. This research has addressed gender issues, particularly how entrepreneurship contributes to changing the status of women in society.

Purple cluster: The Digital Transformation Nexus: This group highlights the effects of digital transformation on women's entrepreneurial processes and how the digital economy offers women an opportunity to become entrepreneurs in a globalized and interconnected world.

Figure 6. Co-occurrence network of the most frequently used author keywords.

Source: Authors

3. Discussion:

The aim of this study was to map the main research on female entrepreneurship and digital technology through a bibliometric analysis of the main research indexed in the Scopus database between 2017 and 2015. It examined the most influential authors and journals, publications, and thematic groupings. The results of this work reaffirm previous studies related to female entrepreneurship, which show a growing interest in research addressing the issue of gender and entrepreneurship, as well as the plurality of themes addressed in this field of research. During the study period (2017-2025), there was a significant increase in studies dedicated to female digital entrepreneurship, rising from three documents in 2017 to sixty in 2025. This growing trend highlights the role of female entrepreneurs in the digital economy. The results of our research are in line with bibliometric studies on female entrepreneurship, which show an increase in scientific research over the last two decades. Henry et al. (2016) showed that scientific output related to female entrepreneurship has grown considerably since the early 2000s, illustrating the scientific interest in gender-related entrepreneurial dynamics. Similarly, Poggesi et al. (2020) observed a significant increase in the literature on female entrepreneurship, focusing on the emergence of new areas of research around innovation and technology adoption in the entrepreneurial field. Digital

tools have enabled women in particular to overcome certain structural barriers such as limited access to financing resources, mobility restrictions, and professional networks (Brush et al., 2019).

In terms of the geographical distribution of publications, developed countries are the most productive in this field, which corroborates studies on female entrepreneurship (Acs et al., 2017). However, India's position at the top of the list shows the contribution of emerging economies to the literature on female digital entrepreneurship. This finding points to rapid digital transformation in developing countries, offering entrepreneurial opportunities for women (Autio et al., 2018). Previous bibliometric research has already reported similar geographical distributions. Poggese et al. (2020) showed that the majority of research in this field is concentrated in Europe and North America, with an increase in research from emerging countries in recent years. Despite this increase in research in developing countries, regional disparities persist in scientific research related to women's digital entrepreneurship. The clusters identified reveal the multidimensional nature of research on female digital entrepreneurship and align with the thematic fields identified in previous studies. The first cluster highlights the importance of digital ecosystems and the infrastructure needed to carry out entrepreneurial activities. Digital technologies promote and offer new opportunities for innovation in business models (Nambisan, 2017). The second cluster emphasizes the importance of financial education and inclusion, which have been identified as critical factors in women's entrepreneurial success. Previous research has shown that women entrepreneurs face greater financing problems than men (Brush et al., 2019). The third cluster focuses on women's empowerment, gender relations, and feminism. According to Jennings and Brush (2013), entrepreneurship research must incorporate a gender approach to better understand how cultural and institutional factors create opportunities for women. Finally, the fourth cluster highlights the role of digital transformation and its impact on the entrepreneurial process. Sussan & Acs, 2017 showed that this transformation is reshaping traditional models and enabling entrepreneurs to be more interconnected through digital ecosystems. This offers women the opportunity to make greater use of digital technologies to create innovative businesses.

Conclusion

This study conducts a bibliometric analysis to quantify the volume of scholarly literature on women in digital entrepreneurship published between 2017 and 2025, the most prolific authors, the leading journals in women and digital entrepreneurship, and the most cited articles. Overall, the results of this research show that scientific output on women's digital entrepreneurship is growing considerably, demonstrating its importance as a subfield of the global literature on female entrepreneurship. These findings complement previous bibliometric studies by supporting the emergence of digital entrepreneurship as an important field of research for gender and entrepreneurship specialists. However, the literature has several limitations. Future research should focus on geographical contexts that have not yet been explored, particularly Africa and Latin America, where research on this topic remains relatively embryonic. Comparative research conducted in different institutional contexts could shed light on how digital infrastructure and the institutional framework impact the performance of women entrepreneurs. In addition, future research should incorporate conceptual frameworks from digital innovation, entrepreneurial ecosystems, and gender studies in order to develop a more extensive analysis of the factors that shape female digital entrepreneurship. Such an approach would strengthen knowledge about the contribution of digital entrepreneurship to inclusive and sustainable economic development.

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